

C-THERM

HOW TO MEASURE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

METHOD SELECTION GUIDE

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What is Thermal Conductivity?

Thermal conductivity is the measure of a material's ability to conduct heat. It is the rate at which heat flows through a substance per unit of temperature difference. It is an **intrinsic property**, meaning that it is independent of material shape or size.

Figure 1: Demonstration of the concept of thermal conductivity.

Thermal Conductivity Measurements: Putting Theory into Practice

Thermal conductivity is a critical material property that **directly impacts performance** in a wide range of engineering and industrial applications, from electronics cooling to advanced manufacturing. Despite its importance, it is often overlooked in early-stage R&D, particularly when the prototypes are designed based on values from literature or online databases.

Figure 2: A thermal simulation of a circuit board system – thermal conductivity is critical for accurate simulation data.

While standard references provide reliable data for pure substances, most materials used in practice are far more complex. Alloys, composites, foams, pastes, and multilayer systems often exhibit thermal behavior that deviates significantly from textbook values due to differences in formulation, processing, and physical form. Thus, in-house thermal conductivity testing is essential for obtaining accurate, application-specific data, especially when working with novel or complex materials.

The Fundamentals of Thermal Conductivity Measurement Methods

There are mainly two types of thermal conductivity measurement methods: **steady-state** and **transient** (unsteady-state) thermal conductivity methods. In both types of measurements, the thermal conductivity is measured by applying a known amount of heat to a sample and measuring its temperature difference.

Figure 3: Typical setup for steady-state methods. A thermal gradient is developed over hot and cold reservoirs.

Steady-state methods apply heat until the temperature difference across the sample completely stabilizes, whereas transient methods derive the thermal properties from the time-dependent response of the sample when the heat is applied. This leads to each method having its own set of capabilities and limitations.

Steady-State Methods

Steady-state methods generally offer high precision and measurement accuracy and are considered the standard for thermal insulator characterizations. However, the steady-state principle of operations implies that the thermal steady state must be achieved before data collection, which requires long test times and demanding sample preparation procedures.

Guarded Hot-Plate

The **guarded hot-plate method (ASTM C177, ISO 8302)** is a steady-state method for measuring thermal conductivity, particularly effective for insulating and low-conductivity materials. It uses a central heater and guard ring to ensure one-dimensional heat flow through a sample.

This method **is considered a primary reference technique** due to its direct application of Fourier's law, and as such is the only method in which the thermal conductivity value is obtained directly. Its key strengths lie in its **high accuracy, repeatability, and suitability for homogeneous, isotropic materials**. However, it requires long stabilization times, large flat samples, and careful insulation, making it less suitable for rapid or field-based testing.

Heat Flow Meter

The **heat flow meter method (ASTM C518, ISO 8301)** is a calibrated method that measures the thermal conductivity of flat, homogeneous materials, particularly insulators, with similar principles of operation as the guarded hot-plate method. While less precise than the guarded hot-plate method, HFM systems are **easier to operate and well-suited for quality control and routine testing**. Limitations include lower accuracy, sensitivity to contact resistance, and reduced suitability for materials with high thermal conductivity or anisotropy.

TIM Tester

The **Thermal Interface Material (TIM) Tester (ASTM D5470-17)** is designed to measure the thermal resistance and thermal conductivity of materials used to enhance heat transfer between surfaces, such as in electronics packaging.

The instrument applies a controlled heat flux through the TIM sample while monitoring the temperature drop across it. This setup enables precise characterization of thermal performance under defined contact pressures and temperatures. TIM testers are valued for their **high accuracy, repeatability, and ability to simulate real-world application conditions**. However, they often require careful sample preparation, precise alignment, and controlled environmental conditions to minimize measurement variability.

Additionally, TIM Testers are capable of measuring **thermal impedance** and **apparent thermal conductivity** of the sample through pressure-controlled measurements. For more information, please access [ctherm.com](https://www.ctherm.com) for blog posts and webinars related to TIM Testers.

Transient Methods

Over the past 25 years, transient thermal conductivity methods have gained prominence due to improved functionality and greater flexibility. Unlike steady-state techniques, transient methods apply heat in pulses or periodic bursts, enabling significantly shorter test durations (**seconds vs. hours**).

Figure 4: Transient thermal conductivity sensors provide fast, versatile means to test materials under representative conditions.

Rapid testing minimizes interference from secondary heat transfer mechanisms like convection and radiation, simplifying experimental setups. Additionally, shorter exposure times reduce the risk of altering volatile components in the sample, preserving material integrity. The compact nature of most transient method equipment supports its transition from R&D environments to quality control applications in manufacturing.

To perform a transient-state thermal conductivity measurement, the sample must be thermally excited by a momentary heat input. There are three main modes of thermal excitation: pulse input, step input, and modulated input. Each heat input scheme is illustrated below in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Excitation methods used in transient methods and their typical temperature responses.

Each heat input can be summarized as follows:

Pulse input: a burst of heat is applied to the sample, causing a rapid rise in sample temperature and an exponential decay. The rate at which the temperature decays is then used for thermal property calculations. An example of a method that utilizes this input scheme is the **Laser Flash Analysis (LFA)** method.

Step input: a constant heat flux is applied to the sample, imposing a transient increase in the sample temperature. The shape of the curve is used for thermal property calculations. **All methods offered on the Trident instrument** use this excitation scheme.

Modulated input: the sample temperature is modulated using a sinusoidal heat input, and the wave characteristics of the temperature fluctuation are used for thermal property calculations. An example of a method that utilizes this input scheme is the **3 ω (Three-Omega)** method.

Innovations in Thermal Conductivity Testing – An Overview of Transient Methods

C-Therm has played a key role in advancing transient thermal conductivity methods, with a focus on delivering reliable and versatile instrumentation. The Trident Thermal Conductivity Instrument reflects this approach, offering users access to four leading transient methods in a single system; when it comes to thermal analysis, **it's better to have options**.

Trident offers the precision of MTPS (modified transient plane source), the flexibility of FLEX TPS (transient plane source), the robustness of TLS (transient line source needle), and the convenience of THW (transient hot wire), **all in one modular package** (Figure 6). These options support a wide range of applications without sacrificing ease of use.

Figure 6: C-Therm Trident thermal conductivity instrument.

MTPS: Modified Transient Plane Source

Single-sided, compact sensor for rapid characterizations.

Polymers: MTPS's fast data throughput is ideal for formulation R&D.

Textiles: MTPS is the only method that complies with ASTM D7984 for textiles characterization.

Insulations: Low thermal conductivity materials can be easily measured by MTPS.

PCMs: The versatility of MTPS enables PCM characterization at pre- and post-transition phases.

FLEX TPS: Transient Plane Source

ISO-certified methodology with multiple supported utilities.

Metals: Both bulk and slab samples with high conductivity can be measured by TPS.

Building Materials: TPS can account for heterogeneity in the building materials.

Thin Films: The *Thin Films* module enables the thermal characterization of thin films.

Thermal Interface Materials: Thermal conductivity is an important parameter in the development of TIMs.

TLS: Transient Line Source

Robust, durable probe-shaped sensor for melts and geological samples.

Polymer Melts: TLS sensors can measure molten samples up to 300°C.

Geological: The robust design of TLS sensors is ideal for geological applications.

Powders: Powders with large granular diameters can be measured with TLS.

Metal Hydrides: TLS sensors can withstand hydrogen under pressure up to 3000 psi.

THW: Transient Hot Wire

Industry's favorite method for liquid thermal characterizations.

Heat Transfer Fluids: THW is often cited in the specs sheet for heat transfer fluids for thermal conductivity values.

Crude Oil: Multi-component fluids, such as crude oil, can also be characterized using THW.

Organic Solvents: Low-viscosity solvents can easily be measured using THW.

Aqueous Solutions: THW's short measurement time minimizes convection.

MTPS: Modified Transient Plane Source Method

Fast and Simple Solution to Thermal Characterization

The **Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS)** Method (ASTM D7984) is a transient-state thermal conductivity measurement method designed for rapid, single-sided, and non-destructive characterization of thermal properties.

Figure 7: C-Therm modified transient plane source thermal conductivity sensor.

The method employs a one-sided heater/sensor, surrounded by a heated **guard ring** (Figure 7). When in use, the heater/sensor sends a short heat pulse into the sample (Figure 8). Here, the guard ring plays a crucial role; it prevents unwanted lateral heat loss, ensuring a more controlled and accurate measurement. **No other vendor offers this patented guard ring technology**, making it a unique and valuable innovation in the field.

Figure 8: C-Therm MTPS thermal conductivity sensor showing sensor assembly and specimen mounting.

This innovative design by C-Therm allows for single-sided, non-destructive testing of samples, providing quick and relative feedback that is highly advantageous in R&D for iterative formulation development and when comparing a range of different samples.

MTPS Capability Overview

The MTPS method applies to a variety of sample types and operating conditions, making it a very versatile solution to thermal characterization. This includes conventional solids like polymers and ceramics, along with liquids and powders, and even challenging materials like textiles and aerogels.

Figure 9: Thermal paste being loaded onto the C-Therm MTPS liquid and powder holder cell.

Another strength of the MTPS method is its ease of use; its plug-and-play design requires minimal operator training to operate. Combined with its short measurement time and single-sided nature of operation, the MTPS method offers simplicity that is unparalleled in other transient methods. This is made possible by the **MTPS calibration technology**.

While the MTPS calibration streamlines the characterization process, this may introduce some additional considerations. That is, the validity of the measured thermal conductivity depends on the agreement of the sample with the calibration materials. Optimal results can be ensured by inputting the **RhoCp** (density and specific heat capacity) data.

The capabilities and limitations of this methodology are summarized below.

Capabilities

- Single-sided, non-destructive testing
- Short measurement time
- Wide range of applicable samples
- Minimal sample preparation required
- Minimal operator training required

Limitations

- Limited high-temperature applicability
- *RhoCp* corrections may be needed
- Delicate sensor chip; may be damaged in some applications
- Contact agent required in most cases to ensure intimate thermal contact

MTPS Application Highlights

Thermal Mapping of Polymer Composites of Filled Systems

Localized thermal properties in filled systems such as polymers and ceramics can be challenging to characterize. MTPS's single-sided, non-destructive, and highly localized measurement scheme, owing to the **guard ring technology**, makes this possible.

Figure 10: Example of a visibly non-uniform filler distribution in a polymer.

To demonstrate this, a clear epoxy was filled with metal nanoparticles in a visibly uneven distribution. Measurements at 9 surface points were used to thermally map the material and correlate with filler distribution.

Figure 11: Non-uniformly filled polymer highlighting (Left) Areas with high and low filler concentration (Middle) MTPS test locations and (Right) Resulting thermal values (W/mK) obtained from the measurements displayed as a thermal map.

Measurements followed expected trends based on visible filler distribution. High-filler areas (e.g., locations 3 and 6) showed the highest thermal conductivity, while low-filler areas (e.g., locations 2 and 9) showed the lowest. Though visual cues alone revealed poor filler dispersion in this case, this method is valuable for opaque matrices or fillers that are not visually apparent.

Accelerated Thermal Conductivity Testing of Aerogels with MTPS

Aerogels represent a class of ultra-lightweight materials that are primarily composed of air (typically >99%). As a result, these materials have very high insulating capabilities (low thermal conductivity) and are extremely low-density. Due to the novel characteristics of the material, it is important to have the capability to effectively characterize its performance.

Figure 12: Silica aerogel sample for MTPS sensor.

Thermal characterization of aerogels via steady-state methods can be challenging, due to sample restrictions that these methods impose; samples usually need to be 10-30 cm in length/width and 5-10 mm in thickness. These dimensions may be impossible to obtain with experimental aerogels, and a measurement may take several hours to complete.

Figure 13: Thermal conductivity measurements of commercially available aerogels using C-Therm's MTPS Sensor.

C-Therm's MTPS method requires samples only 18 mm in diameter and 1-5 mm thick, making it a much more realistic option for testing aerogels. Figure 13 shown above highlights data collected on a variety of aerogel samples using the MTPS. Results were found to be within 4% of the specified values.

Quantification of Textiles “Cool-Touch” and “Warm-Feel”

Touch is a critical performance attribute in material selection and quality control for bedding textiles, automotive, and apparel fabrics sectors. Traditionally, panels of human testers would subjectively quantify whether one material felt warmer or cooler than another, but the sensation of touch is extremely subjective to each person.

To eliminate this subjectivity, thermal effusivity is now widely adopted as the standard parameter for the quantification of touch perceptions of textile materials as per ASTM D7984. The correlation between textiles “warm feel” and “cool touch” is illustrated below in Figure 14.

Figure 14: A diagram showing how thermal effusivity corresponds to haptic sensations of clothing materials.

Using C-Therm’s MTPS sensor, a major Canadian retailer could measure the “warm-feel” of textiles to create thermal underwear and activewear. The Figure 15 below highlights results from four candidate materials in terms of their thermal effusivity.

Figure 15: Measured thermal effusivity values of common textile materials.

FLEX TPS: Transient Plane Source Method

Superior Versatility for Challenging Application Needs

The **FLEX Transient Plane Source (TPS) Method (ISO 22007-2)** uses a heated disc sensor made from a bifilar nickel spiral (two closely spaced windings) encapsulated in a dielectric material such as Kapton® (Figure 16).

Figure 16. C-Therm FLEX Transient Plane Source sensor.

During a measurement, the sensor is placed between two identical samples of the material being tested. A pulse of constant electrical power (lasting up to several minutes) is applied to the spiral, and the resulting temperature increase in the sensor is recorded (Figure 17). This spiral acts as both the heat source and the temperature sensor, allowing the method to capture precise **thermal conductivity and diffusivity** of the material.

Figure 17. Schematic diagram demonstrating the heat flow from the FLEX TPS sensor during a measurement.

In contrast to the MTPS method, the FLEX TPS method can **access the thermophysical properties of the material directly** without relying on calibration data. Additionally, this method allows for full customization of the experimental parameters, including different utilities that are offered with the C-Therm's FLEX TPS system.

Capability Overview

In addition to the standard bulk module, Trident's FLEX TPS system offers three different utilities for measurements, each specializing in different sample geometries and specifications. Their capabilities are summarized below:

Slab

- For thin, conductive samples and in-plane characterizations

Anisotropy

- Specialized module for measuring in- and through-plane properties of bulk materials

Thin Film

- For thin, thermally insulative samples and through-plane characterizations

The utilities allow the FLEX TPS sensor to measure challenging and irregular samples that may not be possible to test with other methodologies. FLEX TPS measurements (except for thin films) also provide direct access to sample **thermal conductivity** and **diffusivity**, which is a capability unique to this method.

Although the FLEX TPS method offers superior flexibility over other methods, it also requires the user to manually input the experimental parameters, and the determination of the optimal parameters requires user experience. The sample requirements are also relatively more stringent than other methods, which may limit the applicability of this method. A summary of capabilities and limitations for the FLEX TPS method is given in the table below.

Capabilities

- Direct measurements of thermal conductivity and diffusivity
- Wide range of operating conditions: **-200 to 600°C / 5000 PSI (configuration dependent)**
- ISO-certified methodology
- Challenging samples can be tested using different utilities

Limitations

- Two identical samples with smooth surfaces are needed for measurements
- Requires a relatively high amount of operator training
- Iterative testing may be needed to determine the optimal experimental parameters

FLEX TPS Application Highlights

FLEX TPS Bulk Utility: Metal Hydrides in Hydrogen Pressure

Hydrogen has gained attention as a clean energy source, but challenges like low energy density and safety concerns hinder its use. Metal hydrides offer promising advantages in capacity, safety, and stability; however, their low thermal conductivity limits their efficiency.

Figure 18: C-Therm FLEX TPS 6 mm thermal conductivity sensor with pelletized TiFeMn hydride powder..

Trident's FLEX TPS method offers a unique capability to measure metal hydrides under hydrogen pressure. This is demonstrated below, where TiFeMn hydride pellets were measured using the TPS method under various gaseous environments.

Figure 19: Thermal conductivity of pelletized TiFeMn hydride under ambient, vacuum, and pressurized hydrogen atmospheres.

The thermal conductivity of TiFeMn pellets changed noticeably with atmospheric conditions: it decreased under vacuum, increased in ambient air, and returned to its initial level when vacuum was reapplied. A significant rise occurred under hydrogen pressure, followed by a partial decrease after venting: still higher than in air, likely due to hydrogen's influence. Repeating the steps confirmed consistent trends.

FLEX TPS Slab Utility: Pyrolytic Graphite Foils

Graphite, a crystalline form of carbon, exists in both natural and synthetic forms and is widely used in applications like lubricants, electrodes, thermal management, and sealants. Their thermal performance improves with greater anisotropy, enhancing conductivity along in-plane directions over the through-plane directions.

Figure 20: In-plane thermal conductivity correlation with microstructure of carbon-based materials.

Due to their thinness and strong in-plane thermal conductivity, graphitic foils are difficult to characterize thermally. C-Therm's FLEX TPS Slab Utility addresses this challenge, as shown in measurements of pyrolytic graphite sheets from HPMS Graphite (**Figure 21**).

Figure 21: In-plane thermal conductivity of flexible and pyrolytic graphite foils vs density.

As expected, there was a strong correlation between foil thermal conductivity and density. This capability to **measure pyrolytic graphitic foils (HGS-12, 12 μm , $k = 1786 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) via the TPS method is unprecedented** at the time this application note was written.

FLEX TPS Thin Films Utility: Thermal Performance of Condoms

Thermal conductivity is an important parameter to consider when developing condoms. It affects the material's ability to conduct heat, affecting user comfort by transferring body heat efficiently, which can enhance the natural feel during use. It also plays a role in material performance during development and serves as a quality control parameter in production.

Figure 22: A Condom in a package.

C-Therm Flex TPS Thin Films can be utilized to assess the thermal conductivity of the condoms, providing insight into the user experience and quality monitoring. Here, **Trojan-BareSkin Latex and Non-Latex** alternatives were measured using the Thin Film utility. The results were also compared with thermal effusivity results from the MTPS method.

Figure 23: Thermal conductivity results of condoms using the FLEX TPS (left) and thermal effusivity results of condoms using the MTPS (right).

The obtained results indicated that the thermal conductivity of latex-based condoms was ~43% lower than that of non-latex condoms (**Figure 23**). Thermal effusivity results followed a similar trend, with the non-latex condoms exhibiting a higher value compared to the latex counterparts.

TLS: Transient Line Source Method

Robust Technique for Liquids, Powders, and Geological Samples

The **Transient Line Source Method** (ASTM D5334, D5930, and IEEE Std 442-1981) is typically used to measure thermal conductivity in materials such as **soft soil, plastic, and liquids**. It relies on a needle probe that is inserted into the sample, ensuring the material starts at a uniform, stable temperature before testing begins.

Figure 24: C-Therm Transient Line Source probe.

A typical needle probe consists of a thin stainless-steel tube with a built-in heating element. During testing, a brief pulse of heat is applied to the probe, creating a heat wave that radiates outward into the sample. At the same time, temperature changes near the probe are recorded by thermocouple sensors.

Figure 25: A typical structure of a TLS sensor.

By analyzing how quickly the temperature rises and spreads, the method calculates the **thermal conductivity** of the material. The simple and robust design of the needle probe allows for accurate and reliable measurement of the sample.

Capability Overview

The TLS method's greatest strength lies in its robustness; to start a measurement, one has to simply insert the probe into the sample and hit "run". The stainless-steel construction of the TLS sensor allows the sensor to withstand physical abrasion to a certain extent, making it applicable to samples that are difficult to achieve smooth surfaces, such as concrete and geological samples.

Figure 26: C-Therm's TLS sensor being inserted into a liquid holder cell.

The sensor is also capable of sustaining high-pressure and temperature environments, from temperatures as low as **-55°C to 300°C and 14500 psi**. Finally, the data analysis is straightforward compared to the TPS method, and as such requires less operator training.

One of the main limitations of this method is its limited range of applicable thermal conductivity: **0.1 to 6 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹**. This limits the application of this method to polymers (on the lower end) and ceramics/cements (on the higher end). Nonetheless, this method still offers a unique capability to test materials that may not be applicable with MTPS or TPS due to their surface quality or their melting properties.

Capabilities

- Robust, simple methodology
- Durable stainless-steel sensor
- Low to minimal training required
- Wide operating range (-55 to 300°C and 14500 psi)

Limitations

- Low applicable thermal conductivity range: 0.1 to 6 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹
- Not effective for non-viscous fluids due to convection effects
- Assumes a radially symmetrical sample; ineffective for anisotropy

TLS Application Highlights

TLS High-Pressure Application: Metal Hydrides in Hydrogen Pressure

Thermal performance of metal hydrides in high-pressure gaseous environments can also be characterized using C-Therm's TLS sensor, which is a capability that may not be available with a hand-held configuration of this method. This allows for metal hydride characterization in powder form in cases where bulk fabrication is not viable.

Figure 27: C-Therm's Trident and a TLS pressure cell.

In this application, the powder forms of the TiFeMn hydride samples were measured using the 50 mm Transient Line Source (TLS) need probe. The powder sample is packed into a cylindrical container and placed into the pressure cell. Below are the measured data from TiFeMn powders under different atmospheric conditions. The trend observed follows that of TPS, which confirms the validity of both datasets.

Figure 28: Thermal conductivity of TiFeMn Hydride powder under different atmospheric conditions using the TLS method.

Measuring Thermal Conductivity of Geological Samples with TLS

Thermal conductivity is a crucial thermodynamic parameter for geothermal and geological applications. Several factors make thermal conductivity characterization of geological samples challenging, such as abrasions from granules, moisture content, and varying degree of porosity. To study such samples in representative conditions, the sensor must be able to withstand physical abrasions during the setup and measurement processes.

Figure 29. Geological samples may contain stones and pebbles that may damage the sensor during a measurement.

Owing to its robust design, C-Therm's TLS sensor offers superior physical resistance without sacrificing accuracy. The results from measuring a potting soil sample using a TLS sensor are shown below in Figure 30. The thermal conductivity of the potting soil sample can be seen increasing with compaction by around 35%, and the presence of moisture further raises the conductivity by around 22%.

Figure 30. Results from measuring thermal conductivity of potting soil sample using the TLS sensor.

High-Temperature TLS: Thermal Conductivity of Polymer Melts

In recent years, the manufacturing landscape has been reshaped by the rise of 3D printing and advanced injection moulding processes. When applying these products in sensitive areas, it is important that the polymer melts used are fully characterized, both for end use and the thermal processing that is involved.

Figure 31: Left) 3D printing system. Right) Trident system with TLS sensor.

C-Therm's High-Temperature Transient Line Source (TLS-HT300) is sheathed in stainless steel, enabling it to measure challenging, viscous materials, including polymer melts safely and reliably. The following data represents the testing of ABS and polystyrene (PS) from room temperature to the maximum temperature of the reference data available (200°C and 280°C, respectively).

Figure 32: Thermal conductivity data of ABS up to 200°C (left) and PS up to 280°C (right).

Compared to the available reference data, thermal conductivity results across the measured temperature range are within 10% of the expected values for both ABS and PS. While reliable reference data above the temperatures listed is not available, the TLS-HT300 can test up to 300°C. PS melt at 300°C was also measured (although there was no reference value to compare), and the measured data followed the expected trend within $\pm 10\%$.

THW: Transient Hot Wire Method

Industry's Choice for Liquid Characterizations

The **Transient Hot Wire (THW)** method (ASTM D7896) is a method primarily used to test liquids and powders, where a thin platinum wire is suspended in a sample to measure their thermal properties. It is commonly used in the automotive industry to characterize the thermal performance of engine coolants.

Figure 33: A Transient Hot Wire Sensor.

The sensor operates on a very similar operating principle to the TLS method, with the main difference being that the sensor wire is exposed in the THW method (see Figure 34 below). This implies that the heat will be applied to the sample directly, and this provides many advantages over other methods for testing liquids and powders.

Figure 34: A schematic demonstrating a THW sensor during a measurement.

Because the heat spread quickly and directly into the sample, the measurement time for THW is much shorter than TLS; as such, certain limitations (such as fluid convection and boundary effects) become less prominent. This provides the THW method with a unique capability for simple and rapid applications.

Capability Overview

The THW method can perform rapid measurements of liquids and powders, owing to the bare-wire design of the sensor. The short measurement time also minimizes the risk of fluid convection and boundary effects that may be prevalent in other methods like TLS.

Figure 35: A THW sensor-cell assembly in front of the Trident Controller.

However, the exposed heating element/sensor is very sensitive to external forces, forbidding applications that may cause the sample to adhere or solidify onto the sensor wire, such as polymer melts and granular particles. When testing materials that may damage the sensor or require a cleaning procedure afterwards, the TLS method may be more appropriate.

Capabilities

- Very short measurement time (less than 2 seconds per run)
- No post-measurement analysis needed
- Small sample volume required for testing

Limitations

- Sample must not react with the exposed platinum wire
- Lower service temperature than TLS (-40 to 200 °C)
- Applications to electrically conductive fluids may be limited (more than 1.5 mS/cm)

THW Application Highlights

Characterizing Thermal Performance of Engine Coolants Using THW

Engine coolants (often referred to as anti-freeze) are an essential working fluid in automotive vehicles; they regulate the engine temperature to prevent overheating, and they also prevent freezing during cold conditions. As a thermal management tool for vehicles, thermal conductivity is a crucial performance indicator of such coolants.

Figure 36. Trident system with transient hot wire sensor (Left) and engine coolant samples (Right).

Below in Figure 37, the results from testing distilled water, ethylene glycol, and a variety of commercially available engine coolants using C-Therm's THW sensor are highlighted. Excellent agreements with literature values for ethylene glycol and distilled water can be seen, and all results from commercial coolants align closely with the expected outcome if applying the rule of mixtures of 1:1 distilled water and ethylene glycol (this is the typical composition of engine coolants).

Figure 37. Thermal conductivity results from various liquid samples.

Fit for Purpose: 4 Points to Consider for Selecting the Best Method for Your Applications

Each method in the Trident package offers unique strengths and capabilities, but they may not yield optimal results when applied to incompatible samples. Here are four points to consider when selecting the best method for your applications.

***Note:** The recommendations given in this document are **guidelines** for method selection. Please contact support@ctherm.com for consultations with our subject matter experts.*

1. Sample Type

The first point to consider when choosing the measurement method is your sample type. Some methods are better suited to a specific sample type, and the compatibility between the method and your sample is essential for optimal data acquisition. The compatibility table below can be used to quickly confirm whether your sample applies to your chosen method.

	Solids	Textiles	Liquids	Pastes	Powders	Aerogels	Geological
	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	✓	X	X	✓	✓	X	✓
	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓
	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X

✓ = Compatible ✓ = Use-Case Dependent X = Not Compatible

For use-case dependent scenarios, please consult our subject matter experts through support@ctherm.com or visit ctherm.com for detailed application notes and webinars.

2. Sample Material and Dimensions

The next step is to confirm whether your sample geometry and material comply with the chosen method. This is especially important when testing solids, since the validity of tests heavily relies on sample geometries.

Testing Solids: Selecting Between MTPS and FLEX TPS

The sample requirements on solids generally depend on the range of thermal conductivity of each material. The following table shows the minimum sample thickness for each method.

Please note that two identical samples must be prepared for a FLEX TPS measurement (four for thin films); that is, samples with the same compositions and surface quality.

	MTPS*	FLEX TPS Bulk/Anisotropy	FLEX TPS Slab	FLEX TPS Thin Films
Aerogels	4 mm	N/A	N/A	N/A
Textiles	1 mm	N/A	N/A	Thickness of 10 to 500µm and size large enough to cover the sensor surface.
Insulations	2 mm	Thickness equal to sensor diameter and diameter equal to 2.5 times the sensor diameter.	N/A	
Polymers	2 mm		N/A	
Ceramics	4 mm		Thickness of 0.01 to 10mm and diameter equal to 2.5 times the sensor diameter (3.5 times for highly conductive slabs).	N/A
Metals with $k < 100 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$	13 mm	N/A		
Metals with $k > 100 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$	See the specialized requirement on the next page.	N/A		

*Samples for MTPS testing must at least cover a sensor diameter of 20 mm.

MTPS High Metals

Conductive materials (typically metals with high conductivity) with $k > 100 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ must be prepared in the dimensions shown here to ensure a one-directional heat flow.

Testing Liquids and Powders: Selecting Between MTPS, TLS, and THW

There are several overlaps in capabilities for testing liquids and powders between MTPS, TLS, and THW, but that does not necessarily mean that they are interchangeable. Below are some guidelines for method selection when considering between these three methods.

	Recommended For:	Not Recommended For:
MTPS (min. 1.8 mL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality and consistency monitoring Testing pure liquids/powders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composite materials (when RhoCp data is unavailable) Granular samples above 0.1 mm diameter
TLS (min. 60 mL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Viscous liquids and granular samples (above 0.1 mm diameter) High temperature melts (e.g. polymer melts) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-viscous liquids Thermally conductive fluids
THW (min. 40 mL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-viscous fluids, especially water or aqueous solutions Oils and Lubricants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Abrasive and chemically active samples (against platinum wire) Electrically conductive fluids

3. Operating Conditions

Depending on your application, experiments may need to be done in non-ambient conditions. C-Therm's Trident package offers high-pressure and high-temperature variants of sensors, but their specifications may differ from their conventional counterparts. As such, it is very important to confirm whether your chosen method can perform measurements at the desired experimental conditions.

Temperature	-50 to 200°C (options for up to 500°C ¹)	-55 to 300°C	-200 to 300°C (options for up to 600 °C ²)	-40 to 200 °C
Pressure (Gas)	2000 PSI	14500 PSI	5000 PSI	N/A

It should be noted that the importance of RhoCp inputs becomes more prevalent when using the MTPS sensor at non-ambient temperatures. The measured thermal conductivity results will still reflect the relative differences between different samples, but the optimal measurement of the absolute thermal conductivity values will likely require the RhoCp input.

The availability of TPS utilities depends on the sensor diameter and variants. To confirm whether your TPS sensor is compatible with the desired utilities, please contact support@ctherm.com.

¹ 500°C configurations for MTPS are for testing insulation and powders only.

² Only consumable TPS sensors are available for 600 °C configurations.

4. Directions of Thermal Properties

Some materials (such as graphitic foils or filled materials) may have **anisotropic** thermal properties, i.e., properties that depend on the **direction of the heat flow**. The **MTPS** and **FLEX TPS** methods support directional measurements, and their testing configurations may need to be considered when selecting the methodology.

Anisotropy: Bulk Materials

MTPS

- The sample can be oriented sideways for in-plane measurements
- If the sample thickness requirement cannot be met, the samples can be stacked to reach the required dimensions

FLEX TPS: Anisotropy Utility

- The utility separates the results from in-plane and through-plane heat transfer
- **RhoCp data** required for the separation of two directionalities

Anisotropy: Thin Materials

FLEX TPS: Slab Utility

- The method measures properties in the **in-plane direction**
- Suitable for samples with thermal conductivity of over $10 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$
- **Thickness data** required for measurements

FLEX TPS: Thin Films Utility

- The method measures properties in the **through-plane direction**
- Like the Slab utility, thickness data for each layer is required
- For radially conductive samples (in-plane conductivity over $\sim 10 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), the sample may need to be cut to match the sensor diameter

Other Transient Methods

Methodologies that are not offered in the Trident package may be desirable in certain applications, such as high-conductivity thin films or very high temperature measurements. This section will entail other notable transient methods that may be applicable in such situations.

Single-Sided TPS

The **single-sided TPS method (ISO 22007-7)** operates on the same principle as the conventional TPS method (ISO 22007-2), but is configured for single-sided measurements. The method measures the sample **thermal conductivity and diffusivity**, and these parameters can be used to obtain the sample **thermal effusivity**.

Figure 38: Single-Sided TPS sensor.

This method is a viable alternative to the conventional TPS method when identical samples cannot be obtained or non-destructive testing is desired. However, the single-sided counterpart does not offer the same degree of accuracy as the MTPS and TPS methods. The capabilities and limitations of the single-sided TPS method are outlined below.

Capabilities

- Thermal effusivity accessible through thermal conductivity and diffusivity
- No contact agent required
- One sample required, whereas conventional TPS requires two
- ISO-certified methodology for thermal effusivity measurements

Limitations

- Generally longer measurement times compared to MTPS
- Relaxed accuracy specifications than MTPS and TPS ($\pm 10\%$)
- Operator dependencies from TPS persist; intensive training may be required
- Does not comply with ASTM D7984

LFA: Laser Flash Analysis

Laser Flash Analysis (LFA), ASTM E1461, measures the **thermal diffusivity** of a material by subjecting a sample to a pulse of radiant energy (typically from a laser or a flash lamp) and measuring its thermal response. Like the TPS method, LFA performs a direct measurement of the thermal diffusivity without the need for prior calibrations.

Figure 39: Example of an experimental setup for LFA.

The main strength of LFA lies in its high-temperature capability; some LFA instruments can conduct measurements in temperatures up to **2500°C** with high accuracy. Additionally, if the RhoCp data are available, the sample's thermal conductivity can be derived from the measured thermal diffusivity.

However, the nature of the experimental setups in LFA may limit the range of applications. The summary of the method's capabilities and limitations is summarized below.

Capabilities

- Direct measurement of thermal diffusivity
- Methodology with one of the highest temperature capabilities
- Thermal conductivity is also accessible through RhoCp data
- Small sample size

Limitations

- Samples may need to be machined to specific dimensions
- Requires samples to be coated with graphite or gold sputter
- Limited to isotropic materials since anisotropy is known to cause significant biases
- Porosity and other irregularities may add complications in data interpretation

FDTR/TDTR: Frequency/Time-Domain Thermoreflectance

FDTR and **TDTR (Frequency/Time-Domain Thermoreflectance)** are novel methods for measuring a sample's thermal properties, where the thermal transport properties are derived from the material's reflectance as a function of temperature. **FDTR** is ideal for non-contact testing of complex structures such as **biological samples and nanostructures**, while TDTR can measure highly conductive materials like **diamond, silicon carbides, or graphene**.

Figure 40: Example of an experimental setup for TDTR.

The main difference between the two methods is the dimensions in which the data analysis takes place (time domain vs. frequency domain). This leads to each method having different sets of capabilities and limitations.

FDTR

Capabilities

- Depth-profiling
- Simpler experimental setup
- Well-suited for low thermal conductivity materials

Limitations

- Additional data (such as $RhoCp$) may be required for accurate analysis
- Signal interpretation can be more complex due to frequency-dependent effects
- Less effective for samples with high thermal conductivity

TDTR

- Studying ultrafast heat transport
- Compatible with anisotropic samples
- Ideal for materials with high thermal conductivity

- Additional data (such as $RhoCp$) may be required for accurate analysis
- Requires complex optical alignment and ultrafast laser systems
- Less effective for insulative samples and depth profiling

3-Omega Method

The **3-omega (3ω) method** is a technique for measuring **thermal conductivity**, especially in thin films, nanostructures, and fluids. An electrically conductive sensor element acting as both a heater and a thermometer is deposited on the sample, and a modulated current is supplied at some known frequency to heat the sample. The voltage changes across the element can be correlated to temperature oscillation, which in turn can be used to derive the sample thermal conductivity data.

Figure 41: A diagram showing a test setup for 3-Omega.

If performed successfully, the 3-omega method can measure samples that conventional measurement methods may struggle with, such as **very thin films (thickness in the order of nanometers)**, **multilayer structures**, and **highly heterogenous materials**. However, this technique is still in its infancy, lacking practical applications and commercialized equipment. The main capabilities and limitations of the 3-omega method are summarized below.

Capabilities

- Small sample requirement
- High sensitivity and accuracy, with different configurations allowing for more customized data acquisition (anisotropy, multilayer, etc.)
- Compatible with irregular or highly localized samples

Limitations

- Traditional fabrication is complex and resource-intensive, requiring precise alignment and calibration
- Performance may be limited against electrically conductive materials or high thermal conductivity films
- Data analysis could become complex depending on the application

Trident Principle of Operations

This section will include the principles of operations behind the thermal conductivity measurement methods offered by C-Therm's Trident Package.

Nomenclatures

A – Slope of resistance versus temperature [Ω/K]	m – Slope of resistance versus the square root of time in an MTPS measurement
α – Thermal Diffusivity [m ² /s]	P – Power supplied [W]
β – TLS calibration factor [Dimensionless]	q – Heat per unit length [W/m]
C – $\frac{1}{m}$ value of the MTPS sensor in vacuum	R – Resistance [Ω]
C _p – Specific Heat Capacity [J/gK]	r – Sensor radius [m]
D(τ) – TPS shape function [Dimensionless]	ρ – Density [kg/m ³]
e – Thermal effusivity [Ws ^{0.5} /m ² K]	T – Temperature [°C]
G – Heat supplied per area [W/m ²]	t – Time [s]
G' – Heat supplied per volume [W/m ³]	τ – TPS characteristic time parameter
I – Current [A]	TCR – Temperature coefficient of temperature [Ω/K]
k – Thermal Conductivity [W/mK]	θ – TPS modified time parameter [s]
L – Wire length [m]	
M* – MTPS m-Star function	

MTPS: Modified Transient Plane Source Method

The MTPS sensor operates by relating the square root of measurement time to the temperature rise on the sensor surface. The temperature rise is measured by using the temperature-resistance relationship of the sensor; the sensor temperature is factory calibrated using the following:

$$R(T) = R_0 + A \cdot T \quad (\text{C1.1})$$

and $R(T)$ is the resistance of the sensor at a given temperature, R_0 is the resistance of the sensor at 0°C, T is the temperature, and A is the slope of the graph of resistance vs. temperature. The slope is equal to:

$$A = R_0 \cdot TCR \quad (\text{C1.2})$$

where TCR is the temperature coefficient of resistance of the sensor. TCR is constant over the measured temperature range and the sensor is calibrated to determine the TCR within this range. Once the MTPS sensor has undergone TCR calibration, the instantaneous surface temperature of the sensor is then:

$$T = \frac{R(T) - R_0}{A} \quad (\text{C1.3})$$

When in contact with sample material, the short current pulse is applied to the heater/sensor to raise its temperature by 1 to 3°C. The rate at which the temperature at the heater/sample interface climbs during the current pulse is proportional to both the input power and the thermal losses due to conduction away from the interface by the sensor substrate and the sample.

Knowledge of the instantaneous temperature of the sensor allows the determination of the thermal characteristics of a material in contact with the sensor. The heat equation for the sensor in contact with the sample and with a constant supply of heat per second per volume, G' , is given by:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + G' \quad (\text{C1.4})$$

Assuming that two semi-infinite media are in contact with the heat generated at the interface and that one medium is represented by the effusivity, e_1 , of the sensor and that the other, e_2 , is the tested sample material (Figure C1).

Figure C1: Schematic diagram of an MTPS measurement.

Then, when temperature of both media at the interface is identical and in thermal equilibrium after contact has been established, the solutions to (C1.4) for the sensor and sample are:

$$\text{(Sensor)} \quad \Delta T_1(x, t) = \frac{2G\sqrt{t}}{e_1 + e_2} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{|x|}{2\sqrt{a_1 t}}\right) \text{ for } x < 0, t > 0 \quad (\text{C1.5})$$

$$\text{(Sample)} \quad \Delta T_2(x, t) = \frac{2G\sqrt{t}}{e_1 + e_2} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{|x|}{2\sqrt{a_2 t}}\right) \text{ for } x \geq 0, t > 0 \quad (\text{C1.6})$$

Where:

- ΔT = the change in sensor surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$);
- G = the power flux supplied to the sensor (W/m^2);
- t = time measured from the start of the process (sec);
- e_1 = equivalent effusivity of the sensor ($= \sqrt{k_1 \cdot C_{p1} \cdot \rho_1}, \frac{\text{W}\sqrt{\text{s}}}{\text{m}^2\text{K}}$);
- e_2 = effusivity of the sample material ($= \sqrt{k_2 \cdot C_{p2} \cdot \rho_2}, \frac{\text{W}\sqrt{\text{s}}}{\text{m}^2\text{K}}$);
- α_1 = equivalent diffusivity of the sensor, m^2/s ;
- α_2 = diffusivity of the sample material, m^2/s ;

k_1 = equivalent thermal conductivity of the sensor, W/mK ;

k_2 = thermal conductivity of the sample material, W/mK ;

ρ_1 = equivalent density of the sensor, kg/m^3 ;

ρ_2 = density of the sample material, kg/m^3 ;

Cp_1 = equivalent heat capacity of the sensor, J/kgK ;

Cp_2 = heat capacity of the sample material, J/kgK ;

$erf(x)$ = integral of the error function

If no thermal contact resistance exists at the interface between the sensor and the sample, then $T_1(x=0, t) = T_2(x=0, t)$ at all points having $x = 0$ and Equations C1.5 and C1.6 become:

$$\Delta T(x = 0, t) = \frac{2G\sqrt{t}}{e_1+e_2} \cdot 0.5642 = \frac{1.1284G\sqrt{t}}{e_1+e_2} \quad (\text{C1.7})$$

From Equation C1.1, the change in resistance of the sensor at time, t , is:

$$\Delta R(t) = R(t) - R(t = 0) = A \cdot \Delta T(x = 0, t) \quad (\text{C1.8})$$

Figure C2 shows a plot of resistance change vs. the square root of time. Once the system has stabilized, the graph shows a linear response with slope m . The inverse of the slope, m , can be written:

$$\frac{1}{m} = \frac{e_1+e_2}{1.1284I \cdot A \cdot G} = \frac{e_1}{1.1284I \cdot A \cdot G} + \frac{e_2}{1.1284I \cdot A \cdot G} \quad (\text{C1.9})$$

How to Measure Thermal Conductivity Method Selection Guide

Figure C2. MTPS sensor voltage response vs. the square root of time. Samples with lower effusivity will yield a steeper slope.

If we consider a measurement in which the “sample” is a vacuum, then e_2 is the effusivity of vacuum, $e_2 = 0$, and Equation C1.9 reduces to:

$$\frac{1}{m}(\text{vacuum}) = \frac{e_1}{1.1284I \cdot A \cdot G} \tag{C1.10}$$

Values of the voltage/time slope, m , for a series of calibration materials with known effusivities can be determined experimentally using the MTPS sensor and a plot of $\frac{1}{m}$ for these materials is linear as shown in Figure C3.

Figure C3. MTPS sensor effusivity calibration curve.

The slope of the effusivity calibration curve is M , and the equation of the calibration line is:

$$\frac{1}{m} = M \cdot e_2 + C \quad (\text{C1.11})$$

where e_2 is the effusivity of the sample, C is the $\frac{1}{m}$ value of the sensor for vacuum, and the slope M is equal to:

$$M = \frac{1}{1.1284I \cdot A \cdot G} \quad (\text{C1.12})$$

Since:

$$C = \text{intercept} = \frac{1}{m} (\text{vacuum}) = \frac{e_1}{1.1284I \cdot A \cdot G} \quad (\text{C1.13})$$

then the equivalent effusivity of the sensor, e_1 , is given by:

$$\frac{C}{M} = \left(\frac{e_1}{1.1284I \cdot A \cdot G} \right) \times \left(\frac{1.1284I \cdot A \cdot G}{1} \right) = e_1 \quad (\text{C1.14})$$

Thus, the effusivity calibration curve allows the determination of effusivity values for both the sensor and the sample. Knowledge of the slope of the voltage vs sqrt (time) response of the MTPS sensor provides $\frac{1}{m}$ values for unknown samples. So long as those $\frac{1}{m}$ value of the unknown material lies within the range of the $\frac{1}{m}$ calibration curve determined using calibration materials of known effusivity, the effusivity of the unknown sample, e_2 , can be determined from the graph in Figure C3 and Equation C1.11.

Two methods may be used to determine the thermal conductivity of a test sample. When the density, ρ , and specific heat, C_p , of the test sample are known, the thermal conductivity, k , can be calculated using the effusivity, determined as described above, and the relationship:

$$k = \frac{e_z^2}{\rho \cdot C_p} \quad (\text{C1.15})$$

Equation C1.15 is also known as the **RhoCp correction**.

If the density and specific heat of the sample are unknown, the thermal conductivity is determined using a graphical method similar to that used for the determination of effusivity. The same $\frac{1}{m}$ data determined for the measurement of sample effusivity is transformed using the m-star function, M^* , which modifies the $\frac{1}{m}$ values such that there is a linear correlation with the sample thermal conductivity. More specifically,

$$M^* \left(\frac{1}{m} \right) = \text{Slope} \cdot k + \text{Intercept} \quad (\text{C1.16})$$

Figure C4: Typical MTPS thermal conductivity calibration curve.

The mathematical structure of the M^* function is based on the dependence between reference thermal effusivity and thermal conductivity. An example of an MTPS thermal conductivity calibration curve, where the modified $\frac{1}{m}$ values are plotted against reference thermal conductivities, is shown in Figure C4 above.

FLEX TPS: Transient Plane Source Method

The TPS method records the temperature rise as a constant power is applied to derive the thermal conductivity and diffusivity of the sample. The sensor temperature response is factory calibrated using the temperature coefficient of resistance (TCR) of the nickel spiral. TCR relates to the change in metal resistance with a temperature change. The power and time of the electrical pulse are calibrated to cause an expected temperature increase in the sensor.

The behavior of the TPS sensor during the transient pulse can be understood in terms of its time-dependent resistance, described by the equation (for small increases in temperature ΔT):

$$R(t) = R_0[1 + \text{TCR} \cdot \overline{\Delta T(t)}] \quad (\text{C2.1})$$

where $R(t)$ is the time-dependent resistance, R_0 is the initial resistance of the TPS element before the transient pulse, TCR is the TCR of the sensor element, and $\overline{\Delta T(t)}$ is the mean time-dependent temperature increase in the TPS sensor element. The temperature increase is dependent on the supplied power, the geometry of the sensor and the properties of the sample. It can also be expressed as $\Delta T(\tau)$ where the variable τ is a non-dimensional characteristic time parameter and is defined as:

$$\tau = (t/\theta)^{1/2}; \quad \theta = r^2/\alpha \quad (\text{C2.2})$$

Where t is the time measured from the start of the transient pulse, r is the radius of the sensor spiral (largest ring), θ is the modified time parameter, and α is the thermal diffusivity of the sample material. In the case of a spiral sensor element (other geometries are possible), the time-dependent temperature increase of the sensor is given by:

$$\overline{\Delta T(\tau)} = \frac{P}{\pi^{3/2} r k} D(\tau) \quad (\text{C2.3})$$

Where $\overline{\Delta T(\tau)}$ is the mean temperature rise of the sensor, P is the input power to the sensor, r is the sensor radius, k is the thermal conductivity of the sample, and $D(\tau)$ is a shape function specific to the sensor geometry and depends on the thermal diffusivity of the sample α . The mean temperature and the shape function can be modified to consider the thermal resistance between the sample and the sensor:

Figure C5: Typical ΔT vs time curve from a TPS measurement.

$$\Delta T(\tau) = \Delta T_0 + \frac{P}{\pi^{3/2} r \cdot k} D \left[\left(\frac{\alpha(t - t_c)}{r^2} \right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (\text{C2.4})$$

where ΔT_0 is the temperature drop on the total thermal resistance between the sensor and the sample and t_c is a time correction that considers the thermal inertia of the sensor and various delays in the electronics of the apparatus. Equation C2.4 is true if and only if the thermal resistances on both sides of the sensor are equal, resulting in steady and equal heat flux to each side.

In essence, the TPS method is based on an iterative algorithm that attempts to match the theoretical curve shown in Equation C2.4 with the measured data (such as the one shown in Figure C5). The thermal diffusivity of the sample will directly influence the curvature of the shape function, and the thermal conductivity will affect the proportionality between $\Delta T(\tau)$ and $D(\tau)$. More detailed mathematical principles of operation for TPS sensors are explored in ISO 22007-2.

TLS: Transient Line Source Method

In the TLS method, constant heat is supplied from the line source (the wire element surrounded by a stainless-steel jacket) and the radial propagation of the heat is recorded as a function of time.

Figure C6: Typical measurement plot from a TLS measurement.

The temperature rise in the line source varies linearly with the logarithm of time as shown in the figure above. The initial, non-linear portion of the curve, is due to heatwave propagation through the walls of the tube and to thermal contact resistance when it is present.

The relationship between the rate of temperature rise and time in the linear region can be used to calculate the thermal conductivity of the sample using the relationship:

$$k = \frac{\beta q}{4\pi \cdot \text{Slope}} \quad (\text{C3.1})$$

Where q is the heat input per wire length: $q = \frac{P}{L}$, and the slope is defined as:

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{\ln(t_2/t_1)} \quad (\text{C3.2})$$

where T_2 and T_1 are temperatures recorded at times t_2 and t_1 , respectively, during the measurement. β is a calibration factor ($\beta = \frac{k_{\text{material}}}{k_{\text{measured}}}$), determined by measurement of standard reference material. k_{material} is the known thermal conductivity of the reference material and k_{measured} is the thermal conductivity of the same material as measured by the method and apparatus being used.

THW: Transient Hot Wire Method

The THW method operates similarly to the TLS method, but instead of sheathing the sensor wire inside a stainless-steel jacket, the wire is exposed to maintain direct contact with the sample. This removes the need for a time region selection (which is necessary in the TLS method), since the temperature-time data can be directly used for the calculation of thermal conductivity.

Figure C7: THW Sensor During a Measurement.

Just like the TLS method, the THW method is based on the solution for the heat transfer equation from a semi-infinite line source in radial geometry, namely:

$$\Delta T = \frac{q}{4\pi k} \left(\ln(t) + \ln\left(\frac{4\alpha}{Cr^2}\right) \right) \quad (\text{C4.1})$$

Where, ΔT : Temperature change [K]

C: $C = \ln(\gamma)$ with γ being Euler's constant, $\gamma = 0.5772\dots$ [Dimensionless]

q: Power (heat) supplied per unit length [Wm^{-1}]

k: Thermal conductivity of the sample [$\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$]

r: The radius of the wire [m]

α : Thermal diffusivity of the sample [m^2s^{-1}]

t: Measurement time [s]

Plotting the temperature rise as a function of the natural logarithm of time will then yield a straight line with the slope $\frac{q}{4\pi k}$. Equating the slope of this line with the term derived in Equation C4.1 above will yield:

$$\frac{T_2 - T_1}{\ln(t_2) - \ln(t_1)} = \frac{q}{4\pi k} \quad (\text{C4.2})$$

With T_i and t_i being the temperatures and times at arbitrary points, respectively (usually taken to be the values at the beginning and the end of the measurement). Rearranging, this expression resolves into:

$$k = \frac{q}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{T_2 - T_1}{\ln\left(\frac{t_2}{t_1}\right)} \quad (\text{C4.3})$$

In the TLS method, the time region chosen for analysis (t_1 and t_2) must be manually chosen by the operator, since the heat must propagate through the wire sheath. Moreover, the overapplication of heat may cause the heat pulse to reach the boundary of the sample cell (the so-called boundary effects) and affect the analyzed thermal conductivity results.

The THW method, however, rectifies this complication by keeping the heating element/sensor in direct contact with the sample. This automates the analysis procedure and removes user biases.

Glossary

Density, ρ . The amount of mass per unit volume. In heat transfer problems, the density works with the specific heat to determine how much energy a body can store per unit increase in temperature. Its units are kg/m^3 .

Heat flux, q . The rate of heat flowing past a reference datum. Its units are W/m^2 .

Specific heat capacity, C_p . A material property that indicates the amount of energy a body stores for each degree increase in temperature, on a per unit mass basis. Its units are J/kg-K .

Thermal conductance, C . The time rate of steady state heat flow through a unit area of a material or construction induced by a unit temperature difference between the body surfaces, in $\text{W/m}^2\text{-K}$.

Thermal conductivity, k . A material property that describes the rate at which heat flows within a body for a given temperature difference. Its units are W/m-k .

Thermal contact resistance, R_c . The temperature difference, at steady state, across the interface of two materials in contact that induces a unit heat flow rate through a unit area. Its units are $\text{K}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{W}$.

Thermal diffusivity, α . A material property that describes the rate at which heat diffuses through a body, defined as $\alpha = \frac{k}{\rho C_p}$. It is a function of the body's thermal conductivity and its specific heat.. Its units are m^2/s .

Thermal effusivity, e . A material's thermal effusivity is a measure of its ability to exchange thermal energy with its surroundings, defined by $e = \sqrt{k\rho C_p}$, with symbols defined as above. It is also referred to as “thermal inertia”. Thermal effusivity may be expressed equivalently in units of $\text{Ws}^{1/2}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$ or $\text{J/s}^{1/2}\text{m}^2\text{K}$.

Thermal Impedance, Z . A sum of thermal resistance (defined below) and thermal contact resistance. It is a measure of how effectively a material can impede a flow of heat, and is defined in units of $\text{K}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{W}$.

Thermal resistance, R . The temperature difference, at steady state, between two defined surfaces of a material or construction that induces a unit heat flow rate through a unit area, $\text{K}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{W}$.

Trident: It's better to have options

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